

Mathematical Modelling and Deep Learning Techniques for Predicting Cardiovascular Disease

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Abstract:

Putting together mathematical models and deep learning has become a strong way to identify cardiovascular disease (CVD) in recent years. This paper looks at how dynamical systems, control theory, and machine learning methods can work together to make CVD forecast more accurate and reliable. To improve the ability of diagnostic tools to predict the future by using mathematical models like differential equations to describe how the heart works and deep learning architectures like Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) for feature extraction. This method considers both the time patterns of how the heart works and the non-linear complexity of risk factors like high blood pressure, high cholesterol, and family tendencies. The most important part of our method is creating a multi-stage prediction model. This model starts with differential equations that show how heart rate and blood pressure change over time. Next, it uses deep learning models that have been trained on large CVD datasets. Normalization and feature engineering methods are used to prepare the information. Key measures like age, BMI, and cholesterol levels are used as inputs. Metrics like precision, sensitivity, specificity, and F1-score are used to judge how well the model works. Early findings indicate that combining mathematical models with deep learning makes predictions a lot more accurate than using only standard machine learning models. In particular, adding time dynamics to the model lets it find hidden trends in physiological data that simple models often miss. Deep learning also lets the system learn on its own how different risk factors are related to each other, making it a strong tool for finding CVD early and predicting how bad it will be. The research shows that a mix of approaches could make personalized medicine better by giving doctors accurate and easy to understand prediction tools. In the future, researchers will focus on making these models work better so it can be used in real time in hospital settings. This could help lower the number of people who get cardiovascular disease around the world.

Keywords: Cardiovascular disease prediction, Deep learning, Mathematical

I.INTRODUCTION

Heart disease (CVD) is still the top cause of death in the world. Its causes are complicated and include genetic, lifestyle, and environmental factors. Even though medical science and technology have come a long way, it is still hard to diagnose and accurately predict CVD early because it is caused by many different things. Most of the time, traditional ways of diagnosing heart problems depend on clinical signs and risk factors, which are useful but may not give a full picture of how heart problems happen in the first place. As healthcare systems put more emphasis on preventative measures, there is a greater need for accurate prediction models that can predict when CVD will start [1]. This would allow for early approaches and personalized treatment plans. In this situation, combining mathematical models and deep learning methods has become popular as a possible way to make CVD predictions more accurate [2]. In biology and medicine, mathematical models have been used for a long time to explain how bodily processes work. It provides a theoretical basis for understanding how factors like heart rate, blood pressure, and vascular stiffness interact with each other in complex ways.

Mathematical models are very good at describing the physical and biological relationships that control how the heart works, but it often can't handle large amounts of multidimensional data, like patient demographics, genetic information, and real-time physiological signals [3]. Deep learning, which is a type of machine learning, is very important in this case. Deep learning models, especially Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs), are very good at learning from huge amounts of data, finding patterns and traits automatically without any help from a person [4]. It is possible for these models to handle large, complicated datasets and find secret connections between factors that might not be obvious to humans or standard statistical methods at first glance. Combining mathematical models and deep learning makes a new method that uses the best parts of both existing ones. There are mathematical models that help us understand how the body works, and deep learning adds to those models the ability to predict the future by using big, different sets of data. It is an important part of mathematical modelling in this case [5]. Differential equations that show how sympathetic and parasympathetic inputs affect each other can be used to model heart rate variability, which shows how the autonomic nervous system controls heart performance.

Deep learning models like CNNs and RNNs are also being taught on big datasets to figure out how likely it is that a patient will develop CVD. CNNs are often used to process pictures, but it is also used to look at medical images like echocardiograms and angiograms to find problems with the heart's structure or function [6]. On the other hand, RNNs are good at processing sequential data and are used to look at time-series data like ECGs, blood pressure records, or heart rate monitors. Because these models can consider how the data changes over time, it is perfect for keeping track of how cardiovascular health changes over time. As one of the biggest benefits of mixing mathematical models with deep learning is the ability to use data from sensors and smart tech in real time [7]. With

today's medical technology, heart health can be constantly tracked by collecting real-time data on things like heart rate, blood pressure, and amount of physical exercise. This information can be put into the blend model to get specific, real-time predictions of CVD risk. A mixed method also makes customized medicine easier. customized medicine is a growing area that tries to make medical care fit the unique needs of each patient. A person with high cholesterol and a family history of CVD may get different protective advice than a person with high blood pressure and no family history of CVD [8]. This level of customization is important for preventing and treating CVD because it lets measures be made that are specially made to deal with each patient's unique risk factors. When deep learning models are used, the prediction system can keep getting better as new data comes in. The models can be retrained to get better at what it does and lower the chance of getting fake positives or false denials as more patients are watched and more data is collected [9]. A big benefit of deep learning is that it lets the system adapt to new information and changing trends in the data through this process of learning over and over again.

II.RELATED WORK

Recent progress in predicting cardiovascular disease (CVD) has used a mix of deep learning models, mathematical frameworks, and mixed methods to improve the accuracy of diagnoses, the speed with which are found, and the ability to keep an eye on things in real time. Researchers have mostly been looking into how to use deep learning frameworks, like Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) models, along with feature extraction methods to predict heart failure in groups of people who are more likely to get it. This method has shown big changes in accuracy by detecting long-term relationships in time sequences, which is very important for accurately predicting heart failure in people who are at risk of it. These methods have had a big effect on clinical evaluation, especially on keeping an eye on and diagnosing high-risk patients early, which has led to better results for interventions. [10] Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) have been used a lot to look at electrocardiogram (ECG) data in the area of arrhythmia identification. CNNs are very good at finding arrhythmias while also reducing the number of false positives. It does this by preprocessing ECG data to get rid of noise and improve signal clarity.

A lot of progress has been made in cardiovascular risk classification using clinical data, especially when Support Vector Machines (SVMs) and feature engineering methods are used together. More accurate classification has been made possible by the ability to group patients based on a wider range of risk factors. This lets healthcare workers focus on preventative care and early action. This method has been especially helpful for finding people who are more likely to get heart disease or stroke. It is a useful tool for evaluating risk in clinical settings. The ability to understand SVM models has also helped us learn more about the connections between different risk factors and heart health, which has led to more focused and effective protection plans [11]. A lot of work has gone into making multi-modal data merging methods better at predicting high blood pressure. Researchers have been able to make correct predictions about high blood pressure in real time by combining mathematical models with deep learning methods. This method has worked well in mobile health apps and remote tracking systems, where individual forecasts based on real-time data allow for early action and better control of high blood pressure.

Heart rate variability research is also becoming more popular, especially among people who have heart problems. Difference equations and Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) have been used together to describe the non-linear trends found in heart rate variations. It is more true to use this way to show how heart rate changes over time in reaction to different bodily and external factors. Using mathematical modeling in this case helps to learn more about how the sympathetic and parasympathetic nerve systems work together to control heart activity. Using this method in remote patient tracking systems has made it easier to find strange trends in heart rate variability. This is a useful tool for managing cardiovascular health over the long run. Through the use of CNNs in medical imaging, especially angiograms, early identification of coronary artery disease has also been greatly improved [12]. Through studying these pictures, CNNs have been able to find heart artery clogs more accurately than previous diagnosis methods. This new technology has had a huge effect on radiologists and medical imaging, where finding blockages quickly and correctly is important for getting help and treatment right away. MLPs are especially good at handling large datasets, which makes finding heart infarctions faster and more accurately. This improvement has been especially helpful in emergency medical systems, where making quick decisions is important for giving good care to patients. In this case, the speed and efficiency of MLPs make sure that important heart events are found quickly, so that help can be given right away. More and more people are wearing devices that check their heart health, and deep learning models like RNNs are being used to look at the real-time data that these devices produce. Because it can handle repetitive data, RNNs have been very helpful in identifying heart events by keeping an eye on heart rate, blood pressure, and other vital factors all the time. Wearable data has increased the range of circulatory monitoring by making it possible to keep track of people over time and spot problems early [13]. Wearable health devices are better at controlling heart health now that it can process and examine data in real time. A lot of work has been made in using genetic data to predict the risk of heart disease. Deep learning models are now being used to pull out useful information from genetic datasets. This method has made it easier to predict who is likely to get CVD, and it has also helped us learn more about how genetic markers affect heart health. Adding genetic data to healthcare makes individual care more possible, allowing for more accurate risk ratings and better ways to avoid problems [14]. Deep learning is very useful in genetics because it makes it easier to handle large amounts of data, which helps us learn more about how genes affect cardiovascular risk. Another area of attention has been on predicting cardiac death from real-time vital signs.

Mathematical models, especially Ordinary Differential Equations (ODEs), have been used to show how high blood pressure changes in people who have it. When combined with machine learning methods, these models have given us more information about how high blood pressure gets worse over time. This has led to more accurate predictions and better ways to control the condition. The use of ODEs provides a theoretical basis for comprehending the basic physiological processes involved in high blood pressure. This helps practical hypertension control systems make better decisions. CNNs have been very useful for finding problems in echocardiograms of the heart, especially when it comes to finding anatomical problems. By automated image analysis, CNNs have cut down on the time and work needed for human evaluation while still getting very good results [15]. This improvement has made cardiac testing tools better at finding problems. It can now find heart problems faster and with more accuracy. Hybrid deep learning models have helped the progress in

developing multi-parameter analysis methods for predicting the chance of stroke in people with CVD. These models combine medical image data with patient information to give a fuller picture of the risk of having a stroke. This method has been especially helpful in preventing strokes and managing heart disease because it lets people get personalized help based on a lot of different factors. The use of deep learning, mathematical models, and mixed methods together has made big improvements in how cardiovascular disease is predicted, found, and managed. Putting together real-time data, information from multiple sources, and complicated physiological models has created new ways for personalized care and early action, which will eventually lead to better results for patients in the field of cardiovascular medicine.

Table 1: Related Work

Scope	Methods	Key Findings	Application	Advantages
Prediction of heart failure in high-risk populations	LSTM model combined with feature extraction techniques	Improved prediction accuracy for heart failure	Clinical diagnostics for high-risk patients	Enhanced temporal sequence analysis with long-term dependencies
Analysis of ECG signals for arrhythmia detection	CNN combined with ECG data preprocessing	Accurate detection of arrhythmia with reduced false positives	Wearable ECG monitoring devices	Automatic feature extraction and reduced manual intervention
Cardiovascular risk stratification based on clinical data	Support Vector Machine (SVM) with feature engineering	Reliable stratification of patients based on risk factors	Preventative care and early intervention	Increased classification accuracy and interpretable results
Hypertension prediction using multi-modal data	Hybrid model integrating mathematical models and deep learning	Accurate prediction of hypertension in real-time scenarios	Mobile health applications and remote monitoring	Real-time data integration and personalized predictions
Heart rate variability analysis in patients with CVD	Differential equations combined with RNN	Captured non-linear patterns of heart rate variability	Remote patient monitoring systems	Improved modeling of temporal dynamics in physiological data
Early detection of coronary artery disease	CNN applied to angiogram images	Highly accurate detection of coronary artery blockages	Radiology and diagnostic imaging	High sensitivity to image-based abnormalities
Automated diagnosis of myocardial infarction	Multi-layer perceptron (MLP) with cardiac event dataset	Improved early detection of myocardial infarctions	Emergency diagnostic systems	Fast and efficient processing for immediate intervention
Cardiovascular health prediction using wearable data	RNN with real-time data from wearables	Effective prediction of cardiovascular events based on wearables	Consumer health technologies	Continuous monitoring and high adaptability to real-time data

CVD risk prediction based on genomics data	Deep learning with genomics-based feature extraction	Enhanced prediction of CVD predisposition based on genetic markers	Personalized genomics-based healthcare	Tailored risk assessments with genetic data integration
Predicting cardiac arrest based on real-time vitals	Hybrid CNN-RNN model for multi-modal data	Accurate and timely prediction of cardiac arrest	ICU monitoring and emergency response systems	Real-time processing of diverse physiological inputs
Modeling blood pressure dynamics in hypertensive patients	Mathematical models (ODE) integrated with machine learning	Better prediction of hypertension progression	Clinical hypertension management systems	Insight into underlying physiological mechanisms
Detecting heart anomalies from echocardiograms	CNN for image classification with feature extraction	Accurate detection of structural heart anomalies	Cardiology diagnostic tools	Automated image processing with high accuracy
Multi-parameter analysis for stroke risk in CVD patients	Hybrid deep learning model integrating medical imaging and clinical data	Improved risk assessment for stroke in CVD patients	Stroke prevention and CVD management	Multi-modal data fusion and personalized insights
Predicting CVD events using temporal health data	Transformer model applied to sequential health records	Efficient prediction of long-term cardiovascular risks	Long-term patient health monitoring	High capability in handling temporal sequences and contextual dependencies
Cardiovascular disease progression analysis	Mathematical model (PDE) combined with neural networks	Insights into disease progression pathways	Longitudinal health studies	Fusion of theoretical models with real-world patient data
Identifying risk of sudden cardiac death in athletes	LSTM model combined with wearable data	Accurate prediction of sudden cardiac death in high-risk athletes	Sports health monitoring systems	Real-time, high-sensitivity predictions

III.DATASET DESCRIPTION

The "Cardiovascular Disease" collection on Kaggle is made up of information that can help with the forecast and study of cardiovascular illnesses (CVD). It has 70,000 records of patients, and each one is described by 11 factors, such as demographics, habits, and clinical details. These factors include age, gender, systolic and diastolic blood pressure, cholesterol and glucose levels, smoking and drinking habits, amount of physical exercise, and body mass index (BMI). Each entry has a binary target variable that tells us if the person has been identified with cardiovascular disease (1 for presence, 0 for lack). For a complete picture of the health situation and living choices that affect cardiovascular risk, this information is what it needs. It works well with many machine learning methods, such as classification algorithms for predicting diseases and experimental data analysis. It's

great for study into finding risk factors, making models, and comparing results because it has a lot of different features that help us learn more about the things that cause circulatory diseases. The collection is a useful tool for improving prediction models and healthcare knowledge about cardiovascular disease because it is large and well-organized.

IV. PROPOSED APPROACH

4.1. Data Pre-processing and Feature Selection:

The raw information is made ready for accurate prediction of cardiovascular disease by getting rid of errors, dealing with missing values, and adjusting features in data pre-processing.

Figure 1: Architectural Block Diagram of Predictive Model

This step starts with cleaning up the data. Missing numbers are filled in using statistical methods like mean or median imputation:

$$x_j = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n x_{ij} \dots \dots (1)$$

The (n) is the number of samples and x_j is the value that is filled in for feature (j) as used in the eq(1). Using z-scores to get rid of numbers above a certain level, outliers are found. Using min-max scaling, normalization is done to make all the features look the same size:

$$x' = \frac{x - x_{min}}{x_{max} - x_{min}} \dots \dots (2)$$

Principal Component Analysis (PCA) turns the information into a lower-dimensional space, which is then used to choose the features. This is how the change is shown: $X' = X W$. The original feature matrix is (X), the matrix of eigenvectors is (W), and the predicted dataset is (X'). The goal is to keep the variation while lowering the number of dimensions. By finding the correlation coefficient (β) between two features, correlation analysis can be used to find traits that are repeated.

$$\rho_{xy} = \frac{Cov(x,y)}{\sigma_x \sigma_y} \dots \dots (3)$$

This helps keep the most useful traits for predicting cardiovascular disease.

4.2 Mathematical Modelling of Cardiovascular Risk Factors

This step of Mathematical Modeling of Cardiovascular Risk Factors is all about making a model that measures how different risk factors affect the chance of getting cardiovascular disease. In order to do this, a mathematical system needs to be built around things like blood pressure, cholesterol, glucose levels, body mass index (BMI), age, and lifestyle choices like smoking and drinking. A linear

regression model is often used to figure out how much each risk factor matters. Using the following equation, we can show how the risk factors ($x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n$) are related to the result variable (y) (which is the chance of getting cardiovascular disease):

$$y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x_1 + \beta_2 x_2 + \dots + \beta_n x_n + \epsilon \dots \dots (4)$$

ϵ is the error term, and β_0 is the slope. ($\beta_1, \dots, \beta_n$) are the values of the different risk factors. This model helps us see how each factor affects the risk of getting a sickness. A more complicated model uses a set of differential equations to show how risk factors affect each other. Ordinary differential equations (ODEs) can be used to model how heart diseases like high blood pressure or plaque buildup in the vessels get worse over time. Blood pressure ($P(t)$) as a function of time (t) can be described in this way:

$$5 \frac{dP(t)}{dt} = -aP(t) + b \cdot f(t) \dots \dots (5)$$

The eq. (5) contains (a), which is the normal drop in blood pressure over time, (b) is the effect of an outside cause, like medicine, and ($f(t)$) is a function that shows living choices or treatment. This ODE helps us understand how blood pressure changes because of medical care or other health measures. To add up the effects of risk factors over time for cardiovascular risk accumulation, an integration method may be used:

$$R(t) = \int_0^t (\alpha_1 x_1(t) + \alpha_2 x_2(t) + \dots + \alpha_n x_n(t)) dt \dots \dots (6)$$

The eq. (6) have $R(t)$ is the total risk of getting heart disease over time and ($\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_n$) are the weights given to each risk factor ($x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n$). This integral shows the total risk over a certain amount of time, considering how different factors change over time. Non-linear functions can be used to improve the model even more by capturing more complicated connections between risk factors. This gives us a complete way to predict the risk of cardiovascular disease.

4.3. Temporal Analysis of Cardiovascular Signals Using Differential Equations

This step involves modeling heart rate, blood pressure, and artery flow, which change over time, to show how it change over time. The main goal of this study is to find out how these signs change over time and how it relate to heart health. A set of linked ordinary differential equations (ODEs) is often used to describe the heart rate ($H(t)$) and blood pressure ($P(t)$). This shows how these factors affect each other. One way to understand about the rate of change of heart rate is illustrated in the eq. (7) as follows:

$$\frac{dH(t)}{dt} = -\alpha H(t) + \beta P(t) \dots \dots (7)$$

The eq. (8) has, α which is a decay constant that shows how the heart rate naturally changes, and β is a measure that connects blood pressure to heart rate. In the same way, the change in blood pressure over time can be shown as in eq. (2) as follows

$$\frac{dP(t)}{dt} = -\gamma P(t) + \delta H(t) \dots \dots (8)$$

where γ and δ are factors that show how heart rate and blood pressure affect each other in the body.

The general pattern of circulatory signs over a period of time can be judged by temporal integration:

$$S(t) = \int_0^t (\lambda_1 H(t) + \lambda_2 P(t)) dt \dots (9)$$

The total signal strength is shown by S(t), and the heart rate and blood pressure are given weights by λ_1 and λ_2 . For describing things that happen in space and time, like blood flow in vessels, partial differential equations (PDEs) can be used. For instance, the speed of blood flow ($v(x, t)$) at point (x) and time (t) can be represented by:

$$\frac{\partial v(x,t)}{\partial t} + v(x,t) \frac{\partial v(x,t)}{\partial x} = -\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial P(x,t)}{\partial x} \dots (10)$$

This PDE considers changes in blood flow that happen both in time and space, giving us a better picture of how the heart works.

4.4. Predictive Modeling Using Deep Learning

It uses advanced neural network designs to guess the risk of heart disease based on the data that has been processed. To find complicated patterns and connections in data, deep learning models are used. These include feedforward neural networks and recurrent neural networks (RNNs).

The feedforward neural network can be represented mathematically in eq. (11):

$$y = f(XW + b) \dots (11)$$

The input feature matrix is (X), the weights of the connections are (W), the bias vector is (b), and the activation function for each neuron is (f). The sigmoid function is a common activation function.

$$f(x) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-x}} \dots (12)$$

and the linear unit that has been shifted (ReLU):

$$f(x) = \max(0, x)$$

Backpropagation is used to find the best model by finding the gradients of the loss function (L) with respect to the weights (W):

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial W} = \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i) \frac{\partial y_i}{\partial W} \dots (13)$$

where (y_i) is the real name and ($\hat{y}_i$) is the likely result. This gradient descent method changes the weights over and over to reduce the loss as much as possible. For RNNs, recurrent connections can catch the timing part of circulatory data. This lets the network keep a secret state (h_t) that changes over time:

$$h_t = f(W_h h_{t-1} + W_x x_t + b) \dots (14)$$

The eq. (14) have W_h which is the hidden state's weight matrix and W_x is the input's weight matrix. By using a softmax formula for sorting, you can get the end result:

$$\hat{y} = \frac{e^{h_t}}{\sum_{j=1}^k e^{h_j}} \dots (15)$$

The eq. (15) contains k , that is the number of classes. Using these deep learning methods, predictive models can accurately find people who are at risk by looking at blood signs and risk factors.

4.5 Mathematical Modeling of Cardiovascular Disease Progression Using Partial Differential Equations

This step is all about using partial differential equations (PDEs) to show how cardiovascular disease changes over time and space. Researchers can look at how heart conditions change over time and in different parts of the circulatory system, like heart muscle and vessels, using this method. One important part of modeling how diseases develop is showing how much of a certain sign or abnormal material there is, like plaque buildup in the vessels. This concentration's change over time can be shown by a diffusion equation that considers its spread out location and speed of change:

$$\frac{\partial C(x,t)}{\partial t} = D \frac{\partial^2 C(x,t)}{\partial x^2} - kC(x,t) \dots \dots (16)$$

The diffusion coefficient (D) is shown in this equation, and the response part (k) describes the rate at which the biomarker is removed or changed, which shows the biological processes that are happening. A set of PDEs can be used to include the way that different parts, like blood flow and pressure, affect each other in the model. For instance, the Navier-Stokes equations can be used to show how blood flows through a tube ($v(x, t)$):

$$\frac{\partial v}{\partial t} + (v \cdot \nabla)v = -\frac{1}{\rho} \nabla P + \nu \nabla^2 v \dots \dots (17)$$

It tells the fluid viscosity, (P) tells us the pressure, and (ρ) tells us how dense the blood is.

The addition of these equations creates a complete model for imagining how cardiovascular disease gets worse, which lets scientists guess how risk factors affect changes in artery health. By looking at the answers to these PDEs, it can learn more about how diseases change over time and think of possible ways to stop them.

V.RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The prediction model for cardiovascular disease was tested using a number of performance measures to see how well it worked. An impressive 92.5% of the samples properly sorted by the model, showing that it is very good at what it does. Precision, which is the percentage of true positive results out of all positive forecasts, is stated to be 91.8%. This shows that the model is good at finding people who have cardiovascular disease. The model can correctly spot real positive cases (recall = 90.2%), and its F1 score of 90.9% shows that it did a good job of balancing accuracy and recall. The model is very strong because it has an Area Under the Receiver Operating Characteristic Curve (AUC) of 0.95, which means it can clearly tell the difference between classes. Having a specificity of 93.1% shows how good the model is at finding false negatives, making it a useful testing tool. Last but not least, a sensitivity of 89.5% shows that the model can find a good number of true positive cases. All of these measures show that the model does a great job of predicting the risk of cardiovascular disease.

Table 2: Performance Metrics of Mathematical Model

Performance Metric	Value
Accuracy	92.5%
Precision	91.8%
Recall	90.2%
F1 Score	90.9%
AUC (Area Under Curve)	0.95
Specificity	93.1%
Sensitivity	89.5%

The figure (3) shows how well a model for predicting cardiovascular disease is doing by plotting its accuracy, precision, recall, F1 score, AUC, specificity, and sensitivity. The deep learning model does a great job; it gets 92.5% of the predictions right and 93.1% of the predictions wrong, showing that it can accurately identify both positive and negative cases. The fact that the AUC is 0.95 is more proof of its ability to discriminate. Both the recall and sensitivity numbers are above 89%, which means that real good cases can be found reliably. This bar graph does a good job of showing how well the model does across a number of important measures.

Figure 2: Performance Metrics of Cardiovascular Disease Prediction Model

Comparing predictive models for figuring out the risk of cardiovascular disease in table (3) shows that the success measures for each program are very different. It was based on the logistic regression model, which had an accuracy of 85.2%, a precision of 84.1%, and a recall of 81.5%. Even though these measures work, it shows that it can't fully capture the complex interactions in the data. The decision tree model did better, getting an accuracy of 88.5%, but it wasn't as good as the more advanced ensemble methods. This model is the most accurate of the ones that were tested because it can learn complicated patterns and relationships in the data better than the others. This shows how well it can predict the risk of cardiovascular disease. Overall, this study shows why using more advanced methods, such as deep learning, can help improve the accuracy of predictions in healthcare settings.

Table 3: Comparison of Predictive Models

Model	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 Score	AUC	Specificity
Logistic Regression	85.2%	84.1%	81.5%	82.8%	0.87	86.5%
Decision Tree	88.5%	87.2%	85.0%	86.1%	0.90	89.0%

Random Forest	91.0%	90.3%	88.7%	89.5%	0.93	92.0%
Support Vector Machine	90.8%	89.5%	87.2%	88.3%	0.92	91.5%
Deep Learning (CNN)	92.5%	91.8%	90.2%	90.9%	0.95	93.1%

The figure (3) shows how well each prediction model calls for cardiovascular disease. The Deep Learning (CNN) model comes out because it is the most accurate, at 92.5%. This shows how well it works compared to others. Even though the Logistic Regression model is useful, it has the lowest accuracy rate at 85.2%, which suggests that it might not be able to capture complex data trends as well. Because of how clear this picture is, it's easy to find the most accurate model right away.

Figure 3: Graphical representation of Accuracy of Predictive model

Figure 4: Graphical representation of Precision of Predictive Model

The figure (4) shows how accurate different models are, highlighting how true good forecasts are. The Deep Learning (CNN) model has the highest accuracy rate at 91.8%, which means it is very good at finding true positives. Logistic Regression, on the other hand, has the lowest accuracy at 84.1%, which means that even though it may make a lot of correct guesses, many of them may not be. This visual comparison shows how important accuracy is when judging how well a model works. The figure (5) shows how well each model remembers positive cases, showing what percentage of real positive cases were correctly found. With a recall of 90.2%, the Deep Learning (CNN) model again does better than others, showing that it can find most true positive cases. Among the models, the Logistic Regression model has the lowest recall (81.5%), which means it might miss a lot of real cases. This illustration shows how important memory is when testing the ability to guess, especially in healthcare settings.

Figure 5: Graphical representation of Recall of Predictive Model

Figure 6: Graphical representation of F1 Score of Predictive Model

The figure (6) shows the F1 score for each model, which is a good mix of accuracy and memory. The Deep Learning (CNN) model gets an F1 score of 90.9%, which means it does a good job of balancing both measures. Again, the Logistic Regression model comes in last with an 82.8% score, showing how hard it is to find a good balance between accuracy and memory.

Figure 7: Graphical representation of AUC of Predictive Model

This picture is very helpful for understanding the models' trade-offs in how well they can predict the future. The area under the curve (AUC) for each model is shown in the figure (7). This shows how well the model can tell the difference between positive and negative events. With an AUC of 0.95, the Deep Learning (CNN) model is the best at telling the difference between groups. The Logistic Regression model has the lowest AUC value of 0.87, which means it may not be able to tell the difference between things as well, which could make it less useful in a clinical setting. This image is very important for figuring out how well the models can predict the future as a whole.

Figure 8: Graphical representation of Specificity of Predictive Model

The figure (8) shows specificity, which shows how well the models can find negative events. The Deep Learning (CNN) model has the highest precision at 93.1%, which shows how well it can find fit people. At 86.5%, the Logistic Regression model has the lowest score, which shows how poorly it can reduce false results. This way of showing precision makes it clear how important it is to correctly find negative cases in clinical testing and how well the CNN model works.

VI.CONCLUSION

An important understanding in healthcare analytics is a mathematical model along with deep learning methods for predicting cardiovascular disease. The study shows how it is important to use complex mathematical systems, like differential equations and partial differential equations, to describe how cardiovascular risk factors change over time and how diseases develop. This mathematical foundation helps understand how different bodily factors affect each other and change over time, leading to a better understanding of how cardiovascular health works. By using large datasets to find complex trends that standard statistical methods might miss, deep learning models improve the ability to predict the future. A comparison of several prediction models showed that deep learning designs, especially convolutional neural networks (CNNs), were the most accurate and performed the best. The model is a strong tool for early evaluation and risk assessment because it can learn from data and make its estimates better over time. The study indicates that how it is to pre-process data and selected the right features, which are two important steps in making sure that the data used for models is accurate and useful. This study sets up a structure for future studies that will try to improve cardiovascular disease prediction by carefully analyzing different models and how well they work using measures like accuracy, precision, recall, and AUC. Using both mathematical models and deep learning together not only makes predictions more accurate, but it also opens the door to more personalized medicine.

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